

Emotional Intelligence Factors Influencing Stress Management and Team Building Skills of Students

Ms. N. Uma Maheswari¹ Dr. M.R.Vanithamani²

¹Assistant Professor, Professor²

Department of Management Studies,

Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract:- This piece of research is about how Emotional Intelligence influences the Team work and stress Management skills of the under graduate students. If an individual need to be successful in life and attain their determined life goals, Emotional intelligence helps in many ways by guiding them to step in to right actions. In this consent, this study aiming on measuring the level of emotional intelligence which has become important day by day. While graduating, majority of the students lag in teamwork and Stress management because of their skewed focus on academic grades only. Corporates are expecting students with very high team building skills and present day's work culture pushes the employees to have strong balance in stressful working environment. This study is about the under graduate students of Arts and Science Colleges in Pollachi Taluk of Coimbatore District. The data required for the research have been collected by using a structured questionnaire. Totally 227 questionnaires were received from the respondents in complete form. The objective of the research is to help the students to be aware of their strengths and weaknesses to face the obstacles in work environment; this would help them to strengthen their ability to manage their work life stress as well as the ability to be a strong player.

Keywords:- Emotional Intelligence, Stress management, Teambuilding, Graduates.

I. INTRODUCTION AND METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Emotional intelligence is comparatively a new field of study during the present years. There are many ways to define the concept emotional intelligence. Some definitions of emotional intelligence focus on the skills or competencies of an emotionally intelligent person, few focuses on behaviours and other few focus on intelligence. When emotional intelligence first came for study in the 1995, it assisted as the lost link in a unusual finding of people with average IQs outstrip those with the highest IQs. Emotional intelligence is “to some degree” in each of us that is an imperceptible. Emotional intelligence includes the capability to convey the emotions precisely and the capability to use those emotions and emotional knowledge to improve thought [1].

Cooper and Sawaf [2] suggested that IQ will become much reduced and the concept of emotional intelligence has become a very scorching topic of psychological research in recent trends. In fact, numerous experts believe that a person's emotional Intelligence quotient is more vital than

their IQ and is certainly a better forecaster of success, quality of relationships, and overall happiness. The emotional intelligence is important to a person in many ways.

As emotional intelligence is serious to high performance, an emotionally intelligent person knows to stay motivated under stress, they will motivate others and also, they know to manage complex interpersonal relationships. High EI level persons will build teams will get better results [3]. Emotional intelligence is a multi-dimensional concept that links emotion and thought to progress human communications.[4]. In recent research, it was found that team performance is completely and knowingly influenced if team is able to recognize emotions of teammates [5]. Further, it was identified that employees having high level of emotional intelligence are have more skilled to normalize their own skill as well as manage others' emotions to encourage positive interactions which would lead to higher performance in the team and also as an individual.

In this present competitive world hardship are widely spread in the life of everyone, and it is nature for an individual to have a stress that is very difficult to overcome. Stress is a common factor that has been known for centuries, but only recently has it started to be fingered scientifically, and the concept of stress requires interdisciplinary studies for understanding its nature.[6] Although we may think our conclusions are based on sound judgment and evidences, the truth is emotions play a vital role in our work life and substantial stress can have an adversative effect on our leadership performance. Stress is one of the major issues to the organization and also to the employees [7]. The person with emotional intelligence will have skills to work in the stressful situation along with other team members.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Nazan Yelkikalan et al., (2015)[8] in their research studied the emotional intelligence levels of university students in the context of emotional intelligence extent the difference in terms of demographic qualities of students and the majors they study and the relationship between emotional intelligence of students and their academic achievements. For this purpose, a questionnaire was filled in by students studying at five different faculties of Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University. The results of the research revealed that there is not any significant difference in the relationship between the faculty of students and their emotional intelligence, apart from the sociability. Besides, it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between the emotional intelligence

and academic achievements and that almost 11 % of change in academic achievements can be explained by emotional intelligence.

Jackson de Carvalho and Alex D.Colvin, (2015)[9] in their study they tell that the emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and to manage the relationship between emotion, cognition and behaviour. It was hypothesized that levels of emotional intelligence are associated with levels of income. Few studies have examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic success among low-income college students. The purpose of this correlation and comparative research study was to test a hypothesized model about students' income level, emotional intelligence skills, and academic success. Relations between variables associated to academic success were explored using multivariate analysis techniques. The results showed significant direct and/or indirect effects of income level on emotional intelligence and academic success.

Amalia Petrovici and Tatiana Dobrescu, (2014)[10] stated that to identify the role of emotional intelligence in developing communication and relational skills. Evaluating the level of emotional intelligence is essential for building efficient communication, intellectual and emotional development. Socrate's advice "Know thyself!" finds its application in this case by self-controlling one's emotions and adjusting them to the context, aiming at the need to know others and interact positively, skills that bring satisfaction and accomplishments to the human being on an individual as well as social level. The paper attends to these imperatives.

Jose L. Antoñanzas et al., (2014)[11] states that emotional intelligence and personality traits are associated with personal satisfaction experienced by the subjects, according to certain studies. In turn, the relationship between personality factors, emotional intelligence and teacher self-sufficiently is also important. A study on emotional intelligence was carried out with 160 students from Faculty of Education at the University of Zaragoza, specializing in the areas of physical education, primary education, foreign language and special education, measuring levels of emotional intelligence and personality traits. The results demonstrated how students with specialties that require a more vocational profile differ from other students who are studying other specialties.

Nicolae Mitrofan and Mihai-Florentin Cioricaru, (2014)[12] focuses on the significance of emotional intelligence in school. A sample group of 136 students attending "Mihai Viteazul" High School in Bucharest have been selected (68 boys and 68 girls) for this study. The Emotional Intelligence Test modified by Rocco (2004) and originally designed by Goleman and Bar-On has been used for gathering data. School performance was determined by each individual's grades at the end of the first semester. Data analysis has revealed that a high emotional intelligence quotient is not correlated with high school performance. Also, data showed that gender plays no role in this correlation.

Hossein Jenaabadi, (2014)[13] aimed to study the relation between emotional intelligence and self-esteem with academic achievement. Statistical population of this study includes 2000 students of Kahnnoj Payam-e Nour University who are completing M.A degree in 2010-2011. 300 students (150 females and 150 males) were chosen randomly as the group sample. Bar-Ann's emotional intelligence questionnaire and Pop's self-esteem questionnaire was used to collect data. SPSS was used to analyze data from descriptive statistic indices including frequency, average and standard deviation, Pearson's correlation coefficient and independent T test. Results showed that emotional intelligence and self-esteem of students had no effect on their academic achievements. Results also showed that self-esteem of female students was higher than that in males.

III. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

➤ *Factors Influencing Team Working and Stress Management Skill of Sample Respondents*

The factors which influence the development of skill among sample respondents are discussed in this section. Namely, influence of gender, influence of family size, influence of other skills like academic skill, intellectual and self-management skill, decision making skill, team working skill and stress management skill are discussed and shown in the following tables.

• *Gender and Level of Team Working Skills*

To inspect if respondents' gender is related with level of team working skill, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Table No : 1 Gender and Level of Team Working Skills

Gender	Level of Team Working Skills			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Male	8	45	17	70
	(11.40%)	(64.30%)	(24.30%)	(100.00%)
Female	25	111	21	157
	(15.90%)	(70.70%)	(13.40%)	(100.00%)
Total	33	156	38	227

The table 1 shows the Gender and Level of Team Working Skills. Out of 227 respondents, 70 (30.84%) are male. There are 157 (69.16%) respondents are female. However, as the calculated Chi-square value is lesser than the table value at five per cent level, there does not exist any significant difference between gender and level of team working skill. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The percentage of respondents who have high level of team working skill is high among male respondents while low level

of team working skill is high among female respondents. Hence, it is found that male respondents are with high level of team working skill.

• *Family Size and Level of Team Working Skills*

To examine if respondents’ family size is associated with level of team working skill, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Table No : 2 Family Size and Level of Team Working Skills

Family Size	Level of Team Working Skills			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Up to Three	2	30	12	44
	(4.50%)	(68.20%)	(27.30%)	(100.00%)
Four	24	105	17	146
	(16.40%)	(71.90%)	(11.60%)	(100.00%)
Five	6	15	7	28
	(21.40%)	(53.60%)	(25.00%)	(100.00%)
Above Five	1	6	2	9
	(11.10%)	(66.70%)	(22.20%)	(100.00%)
Total	33	156	38	227

The table 2 shows the Family Size and Level of Team Working Skills. Out of 227 respondents, 44 (19.38%) have up to three members in the family. There are 146 (64.32%) respondents have four members in the family. There are 28 (12.33%) respondents have five members in the family. There are nine (3.95%) respondents have above five members in the family. However, as the calculated Chi-square value is lesser than the table value at five per cent level, there is no significant association between family size and level of team

working skill. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that the respondents whose family size is up to three members are with high level of team working skill.

➤ *Group of Study and Level of Team Working Skills*

To examine if respondents’ group of study is associated with level of team working skill, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Table No : 3 Group of Study and Level of Team Working Skill

Group of Study	Level of Team Working Skill			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
B.Com	13	44	6	63
	(20.60%)	(69.80%)	(9.50%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-CA	13	48	14	75
	(17.30%)	(64.00%)	(18.70%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-PA	3	11	6	20
	(15.00%)	(55.00%)	(30.00%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-B & I	1	9	0	10
	(10.00%)	(90.00%)	(00.00%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-BPS	0	11	4	15
	(00.00%)	(73.30%)	(26.70%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-Finance	1	8	0	9
	(11.10%)	(88.90%)	(00.00%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-E.Com	2	12	1	15

	(13.30%)	(80.00%)	(6.70%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-CS	0	8	2	10
	(00.00%)	(80.00%)	(20.00%)	(100.00%)
B.Com-ABA	0	5	5	10
	(00.00%)	(50.00%)	(50.00%)	(100.00%)
Total	33	156	38	227

The table 3 shows the Group of Study and Level of Team Working Skill. Out of 227 respondents, 63 (27.75%) respondents are under B.Com course, 75 (33.04%) are under B.Com CA course, 20 (8.81%) are under B.Com PA course, 10 (4.41%) are under B.Com B & I course, 15 (6.61%) are under B.Com BPS course, (3.96%) are under B.Com Finance course, 15 (6.61%) are under B.Com E.Com course, 10 (4.41%) are under B.Com CS course, 10 (4.41%) are under B.Com ABA course. Hence, it is found that the respondents whose group of study is B.Com ABA are with high level of team working skill. However, as the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five per cent level, there is no relationship between group of study and level of team working skill. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

➤ *Team Working Skill – Group Wise*

The Figure 3.5 explains about the team working skill of the respondents according to their group wise. From this figure the respondents who are studying B.Com ABA having high level of team working skill that is 77.90% and the respondents who are studying B.Com B & I are having low of team working skill that is 66.90%.

➤ *Gender and Level of Stress Management Skills*

To examine if respondents’ gender is associated with level of stress management skill, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Table No : 4 Gender and Level of Stress Management Skills

Gender	Level of Stress Management Skills			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Male	8	50	12	70
	(11.40%)	(71.40%)	(17.10%)	(100.00%)
Female	25	113	19	157
	(15.90%)	(72.00%)	(12.10%)	(100.00%)
Total	33	163	31	227

The table 4 shows the Gender and Level of Stress Management Skills. Out of 227 respondents, 70 (30.84%) are male. There are 157 (69.16%) respondents are female. Hence, it is found that male respondents are with high level of stress management skill. However, as the calculated Chi-square value is lesser than the table value at five per cent level, there does not exists any significant association between gender

and level of stress management skill. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

➤ *Family Size and Level of Stress Management Skills*

To examine if respondents’ family size is associated with level of stress management skill, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Table No : 5 Family Size and Level of Stress Management Skills

Family Size	Level of Stress Management Skills			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Up to Three	8	28	8	44
	(18.20%)	(63.60%)	(18.20%)	(100.00%)
Four	19	108	19	146
	(13.00%)	(74.00%)	(13.00%)	(100.00%)
Five	4	22	2	28
	(14.30%)	(78.60%)	(7.10%)	(100.00%)
Above Five	2	5	2	9
	(22.20%)	(55.60%)	(22.20%)	(100.00%)
Total	33	163	31	227

The table 5 shows the Family Size and Level of Stress Management Skills. Out of 227 respondents, 44 (19.38%) have up to three members in the family. There are 146 (64.32%) respondents have four members in the family. There are 28 (12.33%) respondents have five members in the family. There are nine (3.95%) respondents have above five members in the family. Hence, it is found that the respondents whose family size is above five members are with high level of stress management skill. However, as the calculated Chi-

square value is lesser than the table value at five per cent level, there does not exist any significant difference between family size and level of stress management skill. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

➤ *Group of Study and Level of Stress Management Skills*
 To examine if respondents' group of study is associated with level of stress management skill, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Table No : 6 Group of Study and Level of Stress Management Skill

Group of Study	Level of Stress Management Skill			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
B.Com	11 (17.50%)	44 (69.80%)	8 (12.70%)	63 (100.00%)
B.Com-CA	14 (18.70%)	55 (73.30%)	6 (8.00%)	75 (100.00%)
B.Com-PA	1 (5.00%)	16 (80.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20 (100.00%)
B.Com-BI	0 (0.00%)	8 (80.00%)	2 (20.00%)	10 (100.00%)
B.Com-BPS	3 (20.00%)	11 (73.30%)	1 (6.70%)	15 (100.00%)
B.Com-Finance	2 (22.20%)	7 (77.80%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (100.00%)
B.Com-E.Com	0 (0.00%)	12 (80.00%)	3 (20.00%)	15 (100.00%)
B.Com-CS	2 (20.00%)	7 (70.00%)	1 (10.00%)	10 (100.00%)
B.Com-ABA	0 (0.00%)	3 (30.00%)	7 (70.00%)	10 (100.00%)
Total	33	163	31	227

The table 6 shows the Group of Study and Level of Stress management Skill. Out of 227 respondents, 63 (27.75%) respondents are under B.Com course. There are 75 (33.04%) respondents are under B.Com CA course, 20 (8.81%) respondents are under B.Com PA course, 10 (4.41%) respondents are under B.Com B & I course, 15 (6.61%) respondents are under B.Com BPS course, (3.96%) respondents are under B.Com Finance course, 15 (6.61%) respondents are under B.Com E.Com course, 10 (4.41%) respondents are under B.Com CS course and 10 (4.41%)

respondents are under B.Com ABA course. Hence, it is found that the respondents whose group of study is B.Com ABA are with high level of stress management skill. However, as the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five per cent level, there exist significant difference between of group of study and level of stress management skill. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

➤ *Stress Management Skill – Group Wise*

Fig No: 2 Stress Management Skill – Group Wise

The Figure 2 explains about the stress management skill of the respondents according to their group wise. From this figure the respondents who are studying B.Com ABA having high level of stress management skill that is 75.60% and the respondents who are studying B.Com Finance are having low of stress management skill that is 52.22%.

➤ *Level of Team Working Skill and Level of Stress Management skills*

To examine if respondents' level of team working skill is associated with level of stress management skill, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested.

Table No: 7 Level of Team Working Skill and Stress Management Skills

Level of Academic Skill Development	Level of Stress Management Skills			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Low	6 (22.20%)	20 (74.10%)	1 (3.70%)	27 (100.00%)
Medium	24 (14.30%)	127 (75.60%)	17 (10.10%)	168 (100.00%)
High	3 (9.40%)	16 (50.00%)	13 (40.60%)	32 (100.00%)
Total	33	163	31	227

The table 7 shows the Level of Team Working Skill and Level of Stress Management Skills. Out of 227 respondents, 33 (14.54%) have low level of team working skill. Of them, two (6.01%) have low level of stress management skill; 26 (78.08%) have medium level of stress management skill and the rest five (15.02%) have high level of stress management skill. There are 156 (68.72%) respondents have medium level of team working skill. Of them, 23 (14.07%) have low level of stress management skill; 119 (76.03%) have medium level of stress management skill and the rest 14 (9.00%) have high level of stress management skill. There are 38 (16.74%) respondents have high level of team working skill. Of them, eight (21.01%) have low level of stress management skill; 18 (47.04%) have medium level of stress management skill and the rest 12 (31.06%) have high level of stress management skill. However, as the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five per cent level, there exist a significant difference between level of ability to know the strength and weakness and level of stress management skill. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

➤ *Strength and Weakness of the Sample Respondent*

In this section, an effort is made to find out the prominent factor which helps to find out the strength and weakness of the respondent. In general, there are numerous factors are used to find out the strength and weakness and it may differ from one to another. Hence, to identify the most prominent source of factor to know the personal strength and weakness factor analysis is employed and shown in the following table.

Fig No: 3 Factors Which Helps to Know the Strength and Weakness of the Respondents – Factor Analysis

Table No : 8 Factors Which helps to Know the Strength and Weakness of the Respondents – Factor Analysis

Factors	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6	Communality (h ²)
Q78	0.038	0.056	-0.201	0.601	-0.162	-0.184	0.466
Q79	0.011	-0.078	0.186	0.671	-0.282	-0.02	0.571
Q80	-0.173	-0.056	-0.051	0.732	0.092	0.021	0.580
Q81	0.442	0.089	0.126	-0.106	0.518	-0.168	0.527
Q82	-0.078	0.468	0.406	-0.467	-0.153	0.059	0.635
Q83	0.106	0.089	0.673	-0.07	0.284	0.12	0.572
Q84	0.229	0.346	0.532	-0.194	-0.055	0.211	0.540
Q85	-0.031	0.631	0.156	-0.196	0.294	0.097	0.558
Q86	0.284	0.117	0.695	0.024	0.115	-0.075	0.597
Q87	0.371	0.502	0.222	-0.049	0.192	-0.099	0.488
Q88	0.25	0.565	0.465	0.09	-0.003	0.045	0.608
Q89	0.322	0.564	-0.128	0.131	0.176	0.236	0.542
Q90	0.466	0.537	0.134	-0.062	0.059	-0.158	0.556
Q91	0.527	0.196	0.307	-0.075	0.232	-0.008	0.470
Q92	0.472	-0.045	0.267	-0.119	0.369	0.103	0.457
Q93	0.156	0.368	0.244	-0.036	0.46	0.007	0.432
Q94	0.152	0.151	0.208	-0.086	0.274	0.629	0.567
Q95	0.069	0.177	0.063	-0.115	0.687	0.215	0.571
Q96	0.105	-0.009	-0.02	-0.082	-0.036	0.822	0.695
Q97	0.675	0.138	0.109	0.086	0.195	0.025	0.533
Q98	0.621	0.276	-0.049	-0.146	-0.189	0.155	0.545
Q99	0.597	0.325	0.093	-0.043	0.143	0.11	0.505
Q100	0.614	-0.068	0.234	0.016	0.001	0.217	0.484
Eigen Values	5.998	1.796	1.354	1.167	1.133	1.05	
% of Variance Explained	13.208	10.392	9.358	7.684	7.413	6.285	
Cumulative % of Variance	13.208	23.6	32.958	40.642	48.055	54.34	

Six factors are ascertained by locating Eigen values greater than unity. From the rotated component matrix Table 8, it can be seen that “shouting at people”, “insulting others”, “not interested in others problems”, “un-cooperative”, “not understanding people getting emotions” have a component loading of 0.5 and above. Hence, these five variables form first factor.

In factor two, “Experience varied emotions”, “panic easily”, “irritated easily”, “cheating others to get ahead”, “dislike myself”, have a component loading of 0.5 and above.

In factor three, “getting angry”, “feeling sad”, “difficult to approach others”, have a component loading of 0.5 and above. In factor four, “Better than others”, “Empathetic”,

“thinking highly of myself”, “have a component loading of 0.5 and above.

In factor five, “worrying person”, “indifferent to feelings of others”, have a component loading of 0.5 and above. In factor six, “rarely notice my emotions”, “comfortable only with friends”, have a component loading of 0.5 and above.

The percentage of variance to know the strength and weakness explained by these sources in all these factors is also presented in table 8. Based on the component loading, ranking of the variables has been done and shown in the table 9.

Factor one explains 13.208 of variation in knowing the strength and weakness. The second and third factor explains 10.392 and 9.358 of variance in knowing the strength and weakness. The fourth, fifth and sixth factor explains 7.684, 7.413 and 6.285 in knowing the strength and weakness. The total cumulative percentage of variance explained by all these factors is 54.34.

The contribution of a variable in all the six factors is considered for determining the percentage of variations in knowing the strength and weakness of the respondent explained by it. Values of communality show that percentage

of variations explained by a variable. Table 9 reveals that “Insulting others”, “Not interested in others problem”, “Not understanding people getting emotion” and “Un-cooperative” explains the maximum variations in knowing strength and weakness. They account for 53.30 per cent, 54.50 per cent, 48.40 per cent and 50.50 per cent variation respectively in knowing the strength and weakness. “Indifferent to feelings of others – 57.10 per cent”, “Worrying person – 52.70 per cent”, “Comfortable only with friends – 69.50 per cent” and “Rarely notice my emotions – 56.70 per cent” are the factors that account for the least variation in knowing the strength and weakness of the respondent.

Table No : 9 Factors Which Helps to Know the Strength and Weakness of the Respondents – Ranking Based Factor Analysis

Factors which helps to know the strength and weakness of the respondents	Rank
Insulting Others	1
Not Interested in Others Problems	2
Not Understanding People Getting Emotions	3
Un-Cooperative	4
Shouting at People	5
Experience Varied Emotions	6
Irritated Easily	7
Cheating Others to Get Ahead	8
Dislike Myself	9
Panic Easily	10
Difficult to Approach Others	11
Getting Angry	12
Feeling Sad	13
Thinking Highly of Myself	14
Empathetic	15
Better Than Others	16
Indifferent to Feelings of Others	17
Worrying Person	18
Comfortable Only With Friends	19
Rarely Notice My Emotions	20

IV. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS OF THE STUDY

While comparing team working skill and group of study of the respondents the high level of team working skill is among respondents whose is studying B.Com (ABA) course with 50.00%. But the respondents whose is having low level of team working skill is among who studying B.Com course with 20.60%. But as per the analysis the team working skill is not differentiated with group of study. While comparing stress management skill and group of study of the respondents the high level of stress management skill is among respondents whose is studying B.Com (ABA) course with 70.00%. But the respondents whose is having low level of stress management skill is among who studying B.Com (Finance) course with 22.20%. The following are the outcomes.

- Stress will be different for every course depends on their subjects and level of learning skill.
- Each course is differentiated into certain specialization, so there will be differences in the teaching methodology and also environment of the respondents.

- The future career development of the course will give stress to the respondents.

While comparing the level of stress management skill and level of team working skill of the respondents the high level stress management skill is among respondents who are having high level of team working skill with 31.60%. But the low level stress management skill is among the respondent having medium level of team working skill with 14.70%. The following are the outcomes;

- The level of stress management skill is low among those respondents who do not mingle with the other team player to share their problems because of work.
- While working as a team it is necessary to work along with other team player to complete the task. If there is no team work it leads to stress and the individual team player should manage the stress to complete the task successfully.
- For a new team player environment, other persons in the team work and surrounding will give stress and he should know how to manage the stress.

- The level of stress management skill is low among those respondents who do not mingle with the other team player to share their problems because of work.
- While working as a team it is necessary to work along with another team player to complete the task. If there is no team work it leads to stress and the individual team player should manage the stress to complete the task successfully.
- For a new team player environment, other persons in the team work and surrounding will give stress and he should know how to manage the stress.

V. SUGGESTION

After completion of the course the students are not able to withstand in their job because of less skill set and tolerance level. So, while graduating they should be given special training to fill the gap between college and the corporate. Training will improve the sustainability among the graduates. Improving Emotional Intelligence will help to improve good relationship with other members and help them to improve the productiveness and efficiency in work. Now-a-days companies put more pressure on the heads of the candidate. Hence, it becomes difficult to control the emotions and also the work within the team. So, while graduating, the students should be emotionally intelligent to overcome the pressure on their job. Understanding others' emotions and the ability to control our own emotions will make a person to take correct decision which is beneficial to the team and also for company. Improving emotional intelligence will increase the team playing skill of the person. This will help to sustain in a place and adapt any situation to bring better result.

VI. CONCLUSION

Emotional Intelligence will help to improve the skill which is necessary to sustain in the job and also to provide good result to the corporate. Employability of the young demography is a significant factor in the development of economy in the country and the crisis of skill development has to be turned into opportunity to growth, said Dr.C.Rangarajan, Chairman, Economic Advisory Council to the Prime Minister. To increase the employability the students should be given with awareness about the importance of the skill development.

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